

THE CHARACTERISTICS OF PHRASEOLOGY AND ITS
TRANSLATION IN UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Annotation: *English languages is rich in meaningful and colourful phrases. The phraseology of the English language is of particular importance as an object of linguistic research with a specific dictionary composition and charm. It is worth noting the peculiarity of expressing a lot of meaning using a word or phrase. This article is devoted to the study of the features of the translation of phrases with the participation of certain words and evaluate the inner meaning of phraseology.*

Keywords: *translation of phraseological units, stylistic function, stylistic colouring, equivalent application , synonyms, meaningfulness, colourfulness, phrases, aesthetic aspect, rational use.*

English has a thousand-year history. During this time, he collected many phrases that people found successful, well-aimed and beautiful. Thus, a separate layer of language appeared - phraseology, a collection of phrases with an independent meaning. In our country, the study of English is widely established , including good knowledge of English, without knowledge of its phraseology is not possible. Knowledge of phraseology significantly facilitates the reading of both artistic and artistic literature. Rational use of phraseological units makes speech idiomatic. The aesthetic aspect of the language with the help of phraseological phrases, which is literally not translated, but perceived in a rethinking way. “With the help of idioms, with the help of different shades of colour, the informative aspect of the language is filled with an emotional-intuitive image of our world, our life” The world of modern English phraseology is huge and diverse, and every aspect of its study, of course, deserves attention. The purpose of this work is to examine the phraseological units of modern English language derived from artistic and literary

sources. This aspect of the study of phraseologies is of particular importance, because. Most of the phraseological units were mastered from English and other languages artistic literature, while some phraseological units retained their original foreign language form. Borrowing is one of the main sources of replenishment of the English phraseology. Debts from English literature are especially numerous. It is mastered separately from the literature of Latin, Greek, French, Spanish, Italian and other languages. "The etymological aspect of the study of phraseological units in many ways helps to understand the culture and life of peoples in which he or she has mastered this phraseological phrase" For those who are studying English as a foreign language, it is difficult to master this layer of language, but after mastering phraseological unit.

It is known that phraseological units are a language that makes up the dictionary wealth of each language unit and they will be available in ready-to-speech as a unit of language. They also took into account their semantic characteristics, like other language units in the case such as synonymy, antonymia, homonymy, paronymia and polysemia three to events. Phraseological polysemia means the phraseological unit itself and it is understood that it has more lexical meanings. Free, similar in shape meanings from the garden and phraseological unit to a point combined, it can not be regarded as polysemy. Because these are all different phenomena: free a link is a unit of speech, a phraseological unit is a unit of language. For example, take the car dry at dodging or grasp straws are used in drawing up a free combination speech, however straws phraseological units at dodging or grasp dry cart are also available in grammar. From the first, the correct meaning, and from the second, the portable meaning (from the " odd to speak to an excess degree about a work or thing that can not be done " or " no something to hope or help in a difficult situation when there is no way out do and seek") is understood. It is not a language unit of meanings, but two each polysemy does not occur because it means different language phenomena. Above is the attitude (equivalent to The Shape of the phraseological unit with a free link accident) referred to as survivability. If the lexical meaning of the phraseological unit is more than one, then in the same lexemes

as it is done, the main meaning and harvest are determined by the meaning. For example, to insert a jar phraseological unit "broadcast through the mouthpiece" (this has become an old meaning), means "distribute messages to more than necessary level". Also, English-language to make a getaway phraseological unit " committing a crime and "escape from a boring political system" means. The first-the main meaning, the second - the derivative from which it grew. The development of the lexical meaning is also characteristic of phraseological units it is an event. In the present-day Uzbek and English phraseological units, the lexical meaning is mainly developed as a result of the transfer by metaphor. For example, to cheer up the phraseological unit is due to the fact that in the original something to be consumed more often in the dish "get burned" it means This phraseological unit then goes from food to something else, it was also used to look at people, as a result of such a transfer it not coinciding with the nature of the phraseological unit, "the feeling of dislike awakened" meaning is formed. Or English-language to walk all over somebody phraseological there is a similar look in the unit walk. I'm not about to let them walk all over me. 2) but every day is the same repeating the thing touched her heart. We expected Williams to walk all over her. A phraseological unit as a result of the development of a specific meaning the amount of meaning varies. Second phraseological on the basis of one phraseological meaning the birth of meaning leads to two different phenomena - polysemy or homonymy. Homonymy, born with the development of a phraseological meaning, is very small. An example of this.

English and Uzbek at-polysemia when it turns out, it manifests itself in an interesting and enthusiastic state, so on the basis of it knowing how much power he has, he considers himself important, on this basis the transfer led to the birth of a new phraseological unit: the soul came out I -"exhale for the last time" and the soul came out II - " incredibly hard get angry". The second phraseological unit was originally used in the manner of the soul exodus, therefore, by itself, it was distinguished from the first phraseological unit: the previous one if the phraseological unit is used with the relativist of the III person, then the next phraseological unit relativists are used with all three forms of person-number.

Second later in the phraseological unit appeared variants of pronouncing the soul, and in two phraseological the separation into Unity has become even more pronounced. A phraseological unit also refers to contradictory meaningful lexical meanings. For example, the phraseological unit of the origin of the sheath of the heart is a severe excitation means, but such a situation is connected both with anxiety and with joy: 1) I will not be afraid, my son. The heart of a person at that time it goes out of the sheath. 2) as soon as the girl saw her paranoia, the guy's heart could get out of his vagina. This one it can be likened to the phenomenon of enantiosemia.

Most phraseological units are monosemantic. For example, go through the Bahri phraseological unit "to give up what it considers useful", something without waiting until the phraseological unit "talked say", or go over somebody's head phraseological unit " for nothing misunderstanding "ni, get down to brass tacks phraseological unit" an important issue it means" to start a discussion". The polysemantic phraseological units are also significant in the Uzbek language and are used in English less than in the language. No more than two polysemantic phraseological units. the transfer led to the birth of a new phraseological unit: the soul came out I "exhale for the last time" and the soul came out II - " incredibly hard get angry". The second phraseological unit was originally used in the manner of the soul exodus, therefore, by itself, it was distinguished from the first phraseological unit: the previous one if the phraseological unit is used with the relativist of the III person, then the next phraseological unit relativists are used with all three forms of person-number.

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1)"in vain",

2) "grumble"; be living on borrowed time

phraseological unit

two means :1)" live in an unexpected short time", 2) "to death"

like "close Hap". Also head thrust phraseological unit three. The article tries to present its own point of view on the mastered phraseological units of the modern English language, examples are given for each type of borrowing under study. The material presented in this work is based on the study of etymological dictionaries shown in bibliography, English-English and English-Russian phraseological dictionaries.

1. Phraseology as an object of linguistic research

1. Subject and functions of phraseologies

Phraseology (Greek phraseology – “expression”, logos – “education”) is a branch of linguistics that studies stagnant compounds in the language. Phraseologies are also called a set of unstressed combinations in the language as a whole, in the language of a certain writer, in the language of a certain artistic work, etc. Phraseology as an independent Linguistic Science appeared relatively recently. “The topic and tasks, the scope and methods of its study are not yet clearly defined, they are not fully covered” . Questions about the main signs of phraseological units in relation to free word combinations, the classification of phraseological units and

their relationship with the parts of speech, etc., are less developed than others. The problem of "phraseological unit and word" is the close and complex interdependence of various linguistic ties and relations, the aspects of their consideration in this work are incomplete and only possible. At the same time, it is necessary to eliminate the discrepancies existing in the theoretical and practical issues of phraseology by developing common problems that connect phraseology with lexicology. The analysis shows that the problem of " phraseological unit and word " is among the common problems and is currently the most important and least developed, which makes it difficult to theoretically base the phraseological system of the language.

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